

Privatization of Water, a Challenge to the Poor: A Study of Select Works by Environmental Activists

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Abstract: Privatization of water is the transfer of ownership of a natural resource like water from a public sector to a private sector with the motive of making profits by selling water to the common man. Economic Globalisation intensifies natural resource extraction and aggravates environmental exploitation. This poses a threat to the poor as well as to the environment. Extracting large quantities of water leads to water scarcity. The rich could afford to buy water for higher prices, whereas the poor are denied access to clean drinking water. Environmental Activists like Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow have voiced the cause of the poor who are denied water due to privatization of water. Privatization of water is at conflict with the idea of water as a human right. Neoliberal policies favour the market system. It thwarts the concept of Environmental Justice. The present paper attempts to point out the challenges posed by privatization of water to the poor as portrayed in select works of Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow. Their activism will impart environmental justice to the marginalized populations. Both Activists declare privatization of water a failure.

Keywords: Neoliberalism, Privatization of water, Environmental Justice, Environment Activists, Hydro humanities

Introduction

Privatization of water is the transfer of ownership of a natural resource like water from the control of a government or the public sector to a private sector or a corporate power structure with a motive of making profits by selling water to the common man. With the advent of economic globalization, natural resources came to be exploited to serve the needs of the industry or the corporate world. Economic Globalization intensifies natural resource extraction and aggravates environmental exploitation. This has led to a widening gap between the poor and the rich. The rich could afford to buy water for higher prices but the poor are denied clean drinking water as they have no money to pay high prices for water.

Objective

The paper attempts to point out the many challenges posed by privatization of water to the poor. Privatization of water is both a challenge to the poor as well as to the environment. Extracting large quantities of water leads to water scarcity, slows down the natural flow of rivers and streams, leading to pollution and contamination of water bodies. This affects the poor who have no money to buy clean drinking water. They are denied access to fresh water bodies as many water resources are owned by corporates who sell water for high prices. This is a true case of human rights violation.

The late twentieth century saw a growing awareness among activists about the environmental and social consequences of converting water into a saleable commodity. Commodification of water leads to water depletion and water pollution. Fresh water resources became scarce, making people leave their homes and livelihoods. Displacement and lack of resources reduced them to poverty. The issue of privatization of water was addressed by environmental activists in their activists' writings. They have played a major role in resisting water privatization. They have organized grass root level movements to stop appropriation of water resources. They have collaborated with activists at the global

level to put an end to water privatization. Environment Activists like Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow have recorded many instances of wide spread opposition against water privatization , have tried to bring out factual evidences of water privatization in different parts of the world .In all these instances we find that the poor are the most affected . They are denied access to clean drinking water. They have lost their livelihoods when their wetlands were taken away from them to build dams and other infrastructures. Water privatization also poses serious threats to the environment –water depletion and water pollution have degraded the environment. Both these activists have pointed out that Environmental Justice is the need of the hour.

Environment Humanities includes under its blanket term fields like Hydro Humanities and Blue Humanities which talks about man’s relationship with water bodies. The field of Hydro Humanities highlights the impact of human activity on the water world. It explores many incidents of atrocities on water and how it impacted the poor. Water is seen as a commodity with an economic value and not as a common good. Hence the field of Hydro Humanities is integral to understanding the water crisis prevalent in the world in the present as well as in future. Environment Justice Ecocriticism deals with texts that speak about social and environmental issues that ought to be addressed in order to impart environmental justice to those who are excluded from becoming partakers of a natural resource like water. Commodification of water is market driven, helps the corporate to make profits out of selling water, but water is an essential resource, a human right and hence cannot be denied to mankind. As a result of water privatization, conflicts break out between governments and marginalized populations leading to protests against water privatization. Protests and campaigns organized by activists have mobilized communities to bring about social changes .These protest marches and grassroots level campaigns finds vent in works of environmental activists which communicate about environmental challenges posed by neoliberal policies of the corporate and the need to embrace water democracy.

Activists writings comprises of works by activists who resist social issues that cause inequalities in society. There have been many instances of writers, activists and the common man protesting against power structures that unleash exploitation in society. Privatization of water is a case in point. To appropriate a natural resource like water for making profits and denying the common man access to water bodies is a human right violation. Privatization of water has led to protests from activists and the common man in different parts of the world. The protest of the common man in Cochabamba, in Bolivia is a true story of how the public reacted to water privatization. Privatization of water has proved to be a failure. Activists have recorded many instances of campaigns, demonstrations, sit ins and other modes of resistance in their works to make the common man aware of the exploitation and the overuse of a natural resource like water. Industries and corporate companies need extensive use of water for large scale production. The excessive extraction of water has depleted underground water resources, leading to desertification, forcing people to flee to wetter lands in search of water. Activists have been trying to alert the public of this social evil, to mobilize communities into actions that resist water privatization. Through their works they have informed the world of the hidden agendas of the corporate world that privatize water resources .The combined efforts of activists and the common man at the grassroots level have resisted privatization of water and have led to alternatives that advocate social changes and environmental reforms. Activists address human right issues or environmental concerns. In the twenty first century, we see the crisscrossing of human rights and environmental concerns in environmental humanities. Privatization of water is at the same time an environmental issue and a human right violation.

According to Ramachandra Guha and Juan Martinez-Alier in “Introduction” to *Varieties of Environmentalism: Essays North and South*: The environmentalism of the poor, we argue, originate in social conflicts over access to and control over natural resources, conflicts between peasants and industry,

conflicts between rural and urban populations over water and energy. Many social conflicts often have an ecological content with the poor trying to retain under their control the natural resources threatened by state takeover or by the advance of the generalized market system. This ecological content is then made visible by writers and intellectuals associated with such movements.(xxi)

Environmental Activists like Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow have voiced the cause of the poor who are denied water, a human right. In her works, *Globalisations New Wars: Seed, Water and Life Forms*, *Making Peace with the Earth*, and *Water Wars*, Vandana Shiva brings to public attention the power structures that support privatization of water. The World Bank, The IMF and WTO provide financial aid to State Governments to privatize water resources. The World Bank guarantees contracts and profits for corporate giants. The World Bank makes conditionalities—water profits, water apartheid, and all water for some. The control of water is transferred from the state government to corporations. This has led to many inequities in society. Maude Barlow, an Environmental activist in her trilogy *Blue Gold (Blue Gold, Blue Covenant, and Blue Future)* talks about how privatization of water poses a challenge to the poor. In her texts, she talks about the power structures that support privatization of water. The World Bank and the IMF backed transnational corporations control the world's water resources. The government signs away their control on water to the corporate. Water trade is purely based on profit. Water is subjected to the market where distribution is determined on one's ability to pay.

Both Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlowe have enumerated the innumerable challenges posed by privatization of water. Denial of access to essential resources like water is one of the main challenges posed by privatization of water. Vandana Shiva in *Globalisations New Wars: Seed, Water and Life Forms* says, “Water monopolies deny people access to water both by carving

out private property within public water range, and by privatizing public services, which increases water costs. . . .” (4)

The same idea is conveyed by Shiva in *Making Peace with the Earth* where she talks about “half the proportion of people without sustainable access to safe drinking water” (84). Maude Barlow also cites many instances of the poor denied access to water resources.

Privatization of water creates monopolies where a multinational company controls water exploiting the poor and the vulnerable populations. In the absence of a strong regulatory system, or the deregulation of the State government, transnational companies may exploit vulnerable populations by charging excessive prices or providing substandard services. Shiva in *Water Wars* says, “Every level of Government –including regional and local—is now forced to adhere to rules that it did not negotiate or agree to. Policy – making is no longer in the hands of local or national governments but in the grip of large multinational corporations”(97).The same idea is conveyed by Maude Barlow’ in *The Blue Future*:“Transnational corporations often override democracy at all levels of government. The thing we most need . . . is undermined by these powerful interests that write the rules to promote their profits” (213).She also adds that the resource grab affects both environmental protection and the equitable sharing of water. Donald Worster confirms “The hydraulic society of the West is increasingly a coercive, monolithic and hierarchical system ruled by a power elite based on the ownership of capital and expertise.” (7)

The vulnerable populations are dispossessed off their lands, and livelihoods. They are displaced and reduced to mere destitute. Their livelihoods have been affected; the resources that sustained them are lost. They are denied their water rights. Adivasis and Dalit communities are affected. They suffer due to water scarcity and water pollution. Theirs is a true case of human rights violation. Rural women and girl children have to walk miles for collecting water. Displaced populations have lost their communities’ livelihoods and ancestral homes. Privatization has failed to deliver

water to the poor. Barlow writes in *Blue Covenant*,“ Water privatization has failed to deliver water to the poor, undermined the human right to water, taken place at the expense of democratic principles and with minimal accountability to local citizens, and has led to foreign control of water and the creation of monopolies”(60).

Water privatization is focused on profit making rather than serving the public. Water privatization is a plan of the elite. The neoliberal policies of globalization favours free trade and free marketing. They favour global investments and pursue their vested interests by controlling the state governments of other nations. The World Bank gives support to the transnational companies to privatize resources like water. Rivers are dammed and diverted to meet the needs of big water companies. The World Bank gives loans to State governments to build dams which takes away water from the common man. The water in the dams is utilized by the industry and the urban elite. Water privatization has intensified the use of water and its access depends on one’s ability to pay. Barlow in *Blue Gold* points out,“ Water trading as carried out by large transnational corporations, is based on principles of profit, which are driving the price of water out of reach of the poor”(73) .She cites many examples of water rights trading becoming a big business in different parts of the world. Water resources will be governed by the private interests of the corporate and the wells of local farmers will run dry. In third world countries, the poor finds it unable to pay for the rising cost of water. Resources are accumulated or stored to raise prices and enhance corporate profits. The world has become a place where even water, a vital element of man’s existence, is for sale. The profit making agenda of the rich corporate is related again in *Blue Covenant*, “Infact, the private companies became owners of the entire infrastructure. . . They were given licenses to run the water system. . .as well as free rein to charge what they liked, lay off employees and makes much profit as they could” (37). The World Bank stated that water should be treated as an economic commodity which supports the principle that corporations can set water prices high enough to

not only recover the cost of their investment, but also to make profits for their investors. Again in *Blue Future* she speaks about industrial and commercial interests that make profit from what is essentially a public trust. “In the private sector, water rates are set in order to generate profits required to pay private investors”(56). This market oriented pricing violates the right to water. The poor are unable to pay high prices for water. Vandana Shiva also points out the profit motives of transnational corporations in *Globalisations New Wars: Seed, Water and Life Forms*: “the public pay the price while transnational companies make the profit. . . Privatization very quickly leads to a steep rise in the price of water”(82). Shiva in *Making Peace with the Earth* talks about the World Bank making paradigm shifts to private sector conditionalities, “ World Bank loan conditionalities have many paradigm shifts built into them – the shift from water for life to water for profits, from water democracy to water apartheid, from some for all to all for some”(84). Shiva in *Water Wars* states that water business is identified as the most profitable industry - “Large corporations covet this lucrative market” (88). Donald Worster opines: “The concentration of power within human society that comes from controlling water was a deliberate goal of ambitious individuals, one they pursued even in the face of protest and resistance” (20).

While the water companies focus on profit, they fail in public accountability. They do not take the responsibility of providing clean drinking water to the common man. As water becomes a tradable commodity, more underground water resources are extracted. When water becomes scarce they resort to the recycling process or sometimes provide contaminated water to common man. Drinking polluted water makes people sick or spreads diseases. Extraction of underground resources in large quantities leads to water scarcity. Water in large quantities is hoarded by water companies who sell water for high prices whenever water becomes scarce. According to Shiva, “water scarcity is clearly a source of corporate profits” (*Water Wars*99). The impact of water scarcity is felt in many parts of the world which leads to conflicts

and protests. Maude Barlow says “The world’s water crisis is having a devastating impact on quality of life for billions of the world’s citizens caught between the twin realities of water scarcity and water pollution” (*Blue Gold* 51). The current rate of water consumption will lead to depletion of water. Water scarcity has afflicted indigenous people who are deprived of their livelihood. At the same time it has helped transnational companies make profits out of selling water for high prices.

In the words of Karen Bakker, “These crisis are simultaneously discursive, social, and material: the social construction and political mediation of a very real set of deteriorating environmental conditions. In practical terms, it means that (in many cases) access to water is a problem of distribution rather than absolute availability. . . .It suggests that scarcity is socially constructed.” (218)

Water privatization has intensified environmental degradation which also have impacted the poor .Pollution has adversely affected the poor; drinking polluted water has made them sick. Both Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow provide evidences of destruction of water resources. Barlow in *Blue Gold* records how modern industrial cultures have destroyed water bodies due to the corporate control of the world’s water resources and distribution system. “Our modern advanced cultures driven by acquisition and convinced of their supremacy over Nature have failed to revere Nature. The consequences are evident in every corner of the globe: parched deserts and cities, destroyed wetlands, contaminated water-ways and dying children and animals” (4). Damming and diversion of water system is also a source of pollution. Population growth, increase in consumption of water, pollution of the water system, global warming, all affect the earth’s water system. Rob Nixon opines that the environment is subjected to “a slow violence” which “ slowly unfolds environmental catastrophes that present formidable representational obstacles that can hinder our efforts to mobilize and act decisively” (2).

Privatization of water leads to a widening gap between the rich and the poor. Privatization of water is a creation of the global corporate who follow the neoliberal policies of the west. Neoliberal policies are profit oriented. They cater to the needs of the world market system where resources in large quantities are extracted for mass production. Neoliberal global policies deregulate state governments and further the decline of the nation states. Consequently all resources of the state come under the control of a powerful corporate who decides how to distribute resources. As global corporate has a profit motive, resources are sold for higher prices which leads to inequities in society. The rich can buy water with their money power but the poor cannot afford to buy water for high prices which widens the gap between the poor and the rich. The elite of a nation have special water access. Barlow quotes ,“ In many countries of the world, the elite of society are gaining privileged access to water , to greater and greater degrees”(Blue Gold67).The disparity of water access between the rich and the poor was violently protested, but the poor are left behind by governments to fend for themselves. According to Rob Nixon, “for it is those people lacking resources who are the principal casualties are of slow violence. Their unseen poverty is compounded by the invisibility of the slow violence that permeates so many of their lives” (4).Water is a human right and should not create monopolies that widen the gap between the rich and the poor. This widening gap creates inequalities in society leading to protest marches and resistant acts.

Neoliberal policies favored the transnational corporate who rule markets for making profits. This resulted in the erosion of the role of the state government. In the words of Melanie Pichler:

Resource policies were shaped by a withdrawal of the State and the creation of favourable conditions for foreign investors. The pressure of international financial institutions and their structural Adjustment Programs (SAP’S) as well as the global policy shift towards neoliberalism, contributed to these developments. In

these contexts, the roles, rights and responsibilities of states and corporations changed significantly. (4)

Globalization unleashes inequities between individuals, social classes and countries of the world. Globalisation has integrated nations of the world. The movement of goods and services has become a normal state of affairs. But there are people who are apprehensive about the idea of a single global economic system and its aftermath.

“Nonetheless, there is widespread unease about the current state of international economic relations. Activists worry that footloose corporations may undermine attempts to protect the environment, labour and human rights” (Frieden7).

Conclusion

Vandana Shiva and Maude Barlow have declared privatization of water a failure. It has failed to cater to the needs of the common man .The selected texts portray factual evidences of the politics behind privatization of water and how it has impacted the environment and above all the poor. By pointing out the challenges faced by the poor due to water privatization, both these activists have made the public aware of the need to have environmental justice movements that fight inequities and injustices in society. Water is a human right and hence shouldn't be denied to the poor.

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